

THE USAGE OF MOBILE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN CLASS ROOM - 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

The uses of smart phones and other gadgets in the university class room is becoming a culture in the modern age of technology. Some students are using this technology for the purpose of information only. However, it was distinguished that others use mobile phone to receive messages over different applications such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and Viber. It is so significant to understand the impacts of their behaviour. On the other hand, the use of mobile technology effects the teaching strategies. Teachers need to adopt new teaching methodologies to make sure that educational objectives and student's deep learning could be achieved together. It is therefore critical to adopt a balance approach. This paper focus on the use of mobile technology in class room learning and to identify how these technologies are playing role in education for upgrading students' knowledge.

Keywords: Information Technology, Mobile phones, Class room learning, Teaching, and Students, Educational objectives.

1. Introduction

The use of internet in education is important because it offers instant access to available information around the world. Traditional learning and teaching procedures are changing due to the excess of information available through internet resources. Teachers and learners both have instant access to the information on virtually any subject. The fast development of internet resources and its accessibility to conduct learning in virtual environment and it leads students and teachers to adopt new devices and techniques during the process of learning and teaching. In many classrooms across universities and colleges students fetching and using their gadgets and mobile phones in learning processes. It is understandable that learners may use the technology for information related purposes during learning processes in the class rooms. However, some students may use mobile technology and other gadgets to communicate with friends and families through available social applications and other networking sites. Due to this, the author of this research became interested in findings the behaviours of the students in the class room environment. It is interested to find out that how the use of mobile technology and social networking applications effect student's learning process. Research has shown that the use of mobile technology is a great experience for students during the provision of teaching. Mobile technology could be used for efficiency and

effectiveness while collecting information from the web. So, students could use mobile technology for audio recording purposes in the class room. This is how they record teacher's lectures and this further helps students to learn in effective ways. Mobile technology is a great tool for the live polling, if the class room strength is heavy. This will help teachers to understand student's thinking and effective teaching could be delivered through this process.

2. Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the use of information technology and its applications in education especially in the class room environment.
- 2) To identify the benefits of mobile phone technologies in classroom learning.
- 3) To study the new teaching methodologies that can help to balance learning and teaching processes through the use of information system and technology and its available applications.
- 4) To know the how to use of mobile technologies in classroom learning.

3. Research Scope and Limitation

The conducted research will be useful for the education industry as it will help teachers to adopt new teaching techniques and methodologies in the class room environment and to balance to use of information technology and systems. The research is also beneficial to understand the behaviour of the students due to the impacts of the technology and information systems in education.

The scope of the research could be measured through the scope of information technology and its use in the educational environment. Time and available resources could be the possible limitations of this research. From academic and educational point of view, the research will provide a comprehensive approach adopted to understand the use of mobile technology and its role in the education especially in the class room environment. From social aspect, the research will provide an opportunity to understand the behaviour of students and its relationship with technology during the provision of teaching and learning. The scientific value of the research will be the outcomes in the form of recommendations that would be helpful to balance the use of mobile technology and new teaching methodologies to achieve educational objectives

4. Conceptual Framework/ Theoretical Frame work

5. Benefits of using technology in the classroom

It is important to acknowledge that students are already interested and engaged in using technology, this creates many amazing opportunities for schools and teachers to benefit from integrating some forms of technology in the classroom and to make teaching and learning more effective. Here are some of the main benefits of using technology in the classroom.

A. Improves engagement

When technology is integrated into lessons, students are expected to be more interested in the subjects they are studying. Technology provides different opportunities to make learning more fun and enjoyable in terms of teaching same things in new ways. For instance, delivering teaching through gamification, taking students on virtual field trips and using other online learning resources. What is more, technology can encourage a more active participation in the learning process which can be hard to achieve through a traditional lecture environment.

B. Improves knowledge retention

Students who are engaged and interested in things they are studying, are expected to have a better knowledge retention. As mentioned before, technology can help to encourage active participation in the classroom which also is a very important factor for increased knowledge retention. Different forms of technology can be used to experiment with and decide what works best for students in terms of retaining their knowledge.

C. Encourages individual learning

No one learns in the same way because of different learning styles and different abilities. Technology provides great opportunities for making learning more effective for everyone with different needs. For example, students can learn at their own speed, review difficult concepts or skip ahead if they need to. What is more, technology can provide more

opportunities for struggling or disabled students. Access to the Internet gives students access to a broad range of resources to conduct research in different ways, which in turn can increase the engagement.

D. Encourages collaboration

Students can practice collaboration skills by getting involved in different online activities. For instance, working on different projects by collaborating with others on forums or by sharing documents on their virtual learning environments. Technology can encourage collaboration with students in the same classroom, same school and even with other classrooms around the world.

E. Students can learn useful life skills through technology

By using technology in the classroom, both teachers and students can develop skills essential for the 21st century. Students can gain the skills they will need to be successful in the future. Modern learning is about collaborating with others, solving complex problems, critical thinking, developing different forms of communication and leadership skills, and improving motivation and productivity. What is more, technology can help develop many practical skills, including creating presentations, learning to differentiate reliable from unreliable sources on the Internet, maintaining proper online etiquette, and writing emails. These are very important skills that can be developed in the classroom.

F. Benefits for teachers

With countless online resources, technology can help improve teaching. Teachers can use different apps or trusted online resources to enhance the traditional ways of teaching and to keep students more engaged. Virtual lesson plans, grading software and online assessments can help teachers save a lot of time. This valuable time can be used for working with students who are struggling. What is more, having virtual learning environments in schools enhances collaboration and knowledge sharing between teachers.

6. Mobile phones in classroom learning

Allowing mobile devices to be used inside the classroom is still a debateable issue surrounding schools in the Philippines today. School administrators, faculty as well as parents opposed the idea of utilizing mobile devices in the classroom. Though, some schools do allow their students to use this provided that it will be used for instructional purposes only. Students today have their own ways of learning using technology.

From taking notes to creating their own digital magazines is their own way of dealing with lessons. Major adjustments must be made by teachers who are non-digital natives. Efforts must be exercised to come up with the demands of time. We can never come back but instead look forward and look for other opportunities' technology could offer. Effects of Texting, Twitter, and Message.

Because mobile technology is becoming so prominent in children's lives, many schools are attempting to use it for teaching and learning. The report included information about activities intended to develop critical thinking skills, master literacy, learn world languages, and improve skills in mathematics, engineering, technology, and science. Some of these

examples of mobile learning utilized the standard features of mobile devices, while others used new innovative features.

7. Content on Student Learning:

Many teachers today are facing the dilemma whether they integrate mobile devices in their lessons or not. It is a common knowledge that our students today are already glued in using mobile phones for personal usage or for school works.

Teachers need to exert more effort in making the students remain interested in the lesson in spite the many challenges that they are facing in today's generation of learners. Effects on the use of mobile device in the classroom may vary depending on how students will be utilizing it. We must consider new possibilities which we have at our disposal.

Teachers can gain valuable real-time insight into the knowledge of their students and the effectiveness of their teaching. It's about time that we adopt new revolution in the classroom. On the other hand, students alike may get positive results in their learning. Choosing the best options on how to integrate mobile devices in the teaching and learning process can help a lot of ways to improve students' academic performance.

8. Efficiency VS Effectiveness

In education, lecturers can prepare PowerPoint presentations and upload to a Learning Management System rather than have to print a copy for each student. Students can read their course materials on their smartphones even while in bed, rather than have to go to the computer labs on the campus before having access to the materials. As explained previously, all these only speaks of an efficient use of technology.

This means that whereas technology use in education is increasing, several students and teachers only use technology to make them efficient and not necessarily effective. Technology provides a whole new opportunity for doing things in a different way. The powerful features of the mobile technology should be creatively used to make our work effective and to achieve high results. Lecturers must not simply add technology to make learning efficient, they must plan for the creative use of these technologies in the classroom.

9. 5 Ways to Use Mobile technology In the Classroom

Technology is powerful and it can be used in several great ways to make teaching and learning powerful. What can be done and what cannot be done is limited, basically by the creativity of the user. So, the more creative and innovative we get, the more results we'll see with using technology in class. However, I will provide a few examples just to help you get an idea of what an effective use will look like.

1. Use of Audio Recording Feature:

Students often require personal and quality feedback on the work they turn in. Lecturers can make use of the audio recording feature built into most smartphones to provide these personal and yet quality feedback to all students. Research has proven that students not just liked feedback given this way, but even preferred it.

2. Live Polling Tools

Live digital polling/quizzing tools can be used both as welcome and exit tickets in the classroom for formative assessment. Lecturers can use these tools (many of which are free) to determine what students already know and what should be concentrated upon. This can also provide insight into individual student strength and weakness and help give personalized instruction when needed.

3. Creating of Videos

Rather than have students write a 2000-word essay after researching on a topic, where several of them would simply copy and paste paragraphs without necessarily understanding the content, lecturers could ask students to research and create 5 minutes or less video or audio recording of what they had researched about.

4. Chat and Online Discussion Forums

Lecturers can exploit the group chat features of mobile devices to create an online discussion forum to encourage class participation on content topics, even outside the classroom. Students can chat and discuss (with or without the lecturer) while at home or over the weekend on a subject in class to increase understanding of concepts.

5. Use of QR Codes

Quick response (QR) codes are another great way to use mobile technology in the classroom. Links to further resources, complex diagrams and images, solutions to tasks could be coded and made available to students.

There are several more ways by which both students and lecturers can creatively use mobile technology in the classroom. Again, technology is powerful and its benefits go beyond just making our work efficient. It can increase productivity and help us achieve greater results in our work, thereby making us effective.

10. There are also five predominant challenges facing mobile learning today.

1. **Negative Implications:** Some mobile devices may contribute to unethical behavior by students or distraction in the classroom. Mobile devices may also compromise the physical health and privacy of students.

2. **Cultural Norms:** Most teachers and parents currently consider cell phones to be a distraction in school.

3. **Theory of Learning:** At the time of publication, there is no accepted theory of learning for mobile technologies.

4. Differentiation: Mobile technologies are diverse, which presents a significant challenge for teachers.

5. Limitations: Some mobile technologies feature poor designs with usage limitations that may adversely affect learning.

In spite of these challenges, there are several market trends that improve the usefulness of mobile technologies in education. For example, most cell phones include features that were once expensive luxuries. Many cell phones also include GPS technology, and it is now possible to use a large number of software applications on devices from different manufacturers. Finally, many mobile devices now include a touch screen, which improves the way students interact with them.

11. Given all of this information, there are five main goals to which educators using mobile technologies in the classroom should aspire.

1. Educators must seek to understand that mobile language is unique for educational reform. This segment of education requires much research and support from both the public and private sectors to succeed.
2. Educators must develop interventions for mobile learning to promote public understanding of the technology's ability to improve education for children of all ages. One way to accomplish this is by creating examples of mobile technology in education and presenting them to the public.
3. Educators must actively promote the use of mobile technologies in the classroom to the public and to educational policymakers.
4. Educators must prepare for the use of mobile technologies in the classroom by training colleagues to use and incorporate mobile devices into learning.
5. Educators must seek support from the country's leadership for the educational use of mobile technologies.

Mobile technologies are unlikely to depart from children's lives any time soon. The potential of these devices for educational use cannot be ignored. While the debate has always been whether or not these devices have a place in the classroom, educators should now focus on how they can be used.

12. Conclusion

The use of mobile learning technology effects students' knowledge improvement in academic performance. Alternatively, the educational objectives got a direct link between with the use of mobile technology in the class room environments. It is impossible to stop students from using mobile during the course of lecture deliver and therefore teachers need to adopt new techniques and methodologies to balance this and overcome issues raised due to the use of mobile applications. It is equally important to look on the students learning capabilities and teachers who use mobile technology during the course of their lecture delivery for the better educational improvement. Finally, am going to conclude that using mobile technology in class room learning will make students to act smart in all stages.

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